

RATE-DEPENDENT RESPONSE OF GRAPHITE/EPOXY IN TRANSVERSE SHEAR

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ABSTRACT

Punch shear experiments are conducted on a 24 ply graphite/epoxy AS4/3501-6 quasi-isotropic lay-up over a range of loading rates. High rate experiments are performed using a punch shear version of the split Hopkinson bar apparatus. Peak punch load and displacement at the peak are found to be relatively insensitive to the punching speed. The lower portion of the curve, however, which is thought to reflect the matrix cracking response, is seen to exhibit substantial rate-dependence. Optical microscopy of sectioned samples of partially punched specimens is used to construct a sequence of the damage process.

INTRODUCTION

The increasing use of composite materials in applications involving severe dynamic loading requires a better understanding of the material rate-dependent behavior. Typical impact experiments involving a spherical impactor onto a composite plate are useful for simulating certain types of service conditions, but the complicated states of deformation, stress, and damage that develop during this type of loading make their usefulness for understanding constitutive behavior somewhat limited. As a result, efforts to perform numerical simulations of impact or other dynamic loadings on composite materials often rely on linear elastic, rate-independent, constitutive models and failure criteria based on static loading. Development of more sophisticated constitutive models and failure criteria has been hampered in a large part by a lack of experiments. What is required are simpler experiments performed over a range of loading rates in which a single dominant stress component can be isolated. In this paper we consider the punch shear experiment as one such experiment. By using a punch bar and die tube having a gap of only 0.03 mm a region of high transverse shear stress is established. A modified version of this punch bar technique has recently been used by Lee and Sun [1] to study penetration of laminated composites. In their version, however, the punch bar diameter is much smaller than the diameter of the supporting die. This results in significant bending of the specimen and therefore a more complex stress field, similar to that produced on the impact of plates by a central impactor, discussed above.

Transverse shear of woven glass/epoxy composites was studied by Harding [2] using the punch shear version of the Hopkinson bar. Two difficulties with the punch shear configuration noted by Harding should be discussed. The first was a lack of repeatability in results. As was pointed out by Harding, however, this difficulty most likely resulted from the coarseness of the woven glass/epoxy specimens that were studied. These experiments resulted in specimens that completely disintegrated upon loading from the Hopkinson bar apparatus. This indicates that influence of the specimen edges are having an effect on the results, which is undesirable. Harding also performed experiments on a fine-weave glass mat. These experiments showed much less scatter and the impacted specimen showed a fairly clean punched hole. In the experiments conducted in this research the laminates were fabricated from unidirectional prepreg containing AS4 graphite fibers, which were considered fine enough so as not to effect reproducibility. The second problem noted by Harding has to do with interpretation of results. The recorded strain histories of the pulses on the incident and transmitter Hopkinson bars are used to obtain force and displacement histories for the specimen, using one-dimensional elastic relations for the bars. These resulting force-displacement relations can be converted to

equivalent stress-strain relations only by making assumptions as to the effective gage length over which the displacement occurs. One possible assumption for the gage length in the punch shear test is to use the radial clearance between the punch bar and the die tube. This, however, results in unrealistically high values of strain. In punch shear experiments performed on metals, Dowling, Harding, and Campbell [3] used the width of the plastic zone, which was obtained from hardness measurements performed on the sectioned samples, to estimate the gage length. Using this method stress-strain curves for various rates were obtained which were in agreement with those obtained using other methods. Unfortunately, no comparable zone exists for laminated polymer composites. Without a suitable estimate of gage length the alternative is to report only the load displacement results. In this way rate-effects, if they exist, can still be seen, without providing misleading results. Although, stress-strain curves are not obtained directly from the results, the tests still can be extremely useful for development of constitutive models, which is the overall goal of the experiments performed here. To do this, the experimental results are being used in conjunction with a finite-element analysis of the test configuration. A constitutive model for the composite material is assumed with estimates for material parameters. Comparison of the computed force displacement with that measured from the experiment over the range of loading rates serves as the basis for acceptability of the material parameters. Iteration of the computation is performed until the desired agreement is obtained.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

To determine the behavior of the graphite/epoxy in transverse shear, experiments were conducted over a range of rates. At low and medium punch velocities, experiments were performed using a specially designed fixture in an MTS hydraulic load frame, shown in Fig. 1. The high velocity experiments were conducted using the Hopkinson bar apparatus discussed below. The same punch/die configuration was used in both cases. The punch diameter is $9.47 \text{ mm} \pm 0.01 \text{ mm}$ and the die inside diameter is $9.53 \text{ mm} \pm 0.01 \text{ mm}$, giving a nominal radial clearance of 0.03 mm. The die outside diameter is $12.70 \pm 0.01 \text{ mm}$. The experiments were conducted on a 24 ply AS4/3501-6 quasi-isotropic [+45/-45/0/90]_{3s} lay-up with resulting thickness of 3.3 mm.

The split Hopkinson bar or Kolsky bar technique has been used extensively to determine high rate properties of materials for several decades. A schematic of the Hopkinson bar apparatus used is shown in Fig. 2. The striker, incident, and transmitter bar are fabricated from tool steel O1 (unquenched). Lack of heat treatment results in a relatively low yield stress, which limits the impact velocity that can be considered. For the composite material considered here, however, this limit presents no severe difficulties. The length of the incident and transmitted bar is .864 m and .762 m, respectively. Two different strikers of lengths 0.406 m and 0.203 m were used to produce different pulse lengths.

Figure 1. Static test fixture

Figure 2. Schematic of Hopkinson Bar Apparatus

The bars are supported approximately every 250 mm on Delran bushings. The specimen is loosely supported between the incident and transmitter bars. Alignment of the bars is performed primarily by feel, without the use of sophisticated optical equipment. The striker bar is supported continuously on a slide with surfaces of PMMA. The striker itself is propelled by a gas gun. Control of the pressure through a regulator is used to bring the striker bar to the desired velocity. The kinetic energy in the transmitter bar is absorbed by a momentum trap placed at the far end of the bar.

Strain gages are located mid-length of both the transmitter and incident bars. The gages used on the bars are 1000 ohms (Measurement Group EA-06-250BK-10C) connected in a half Wheatstone bridge arrangement. Data acquisition is performed with a Nicolet Pro 40 digital oscilloscope, with 12 bits vertical resolution at a sampling rate of 10 Ms/s. By using a 10 V potential difference across the bridge, no signal amplification is required. Velocity of the striker bar is measured independently using phototransistor detectors and an NES Slimline DS1559 timer.

The procedure for determining the load and displacement histories in the specimen from the strain gage readings on the incident and transmitted bars is based on uniaxial wave propagation theory. The method is well established and discussed in detail elsewhere [4].

RESULTS

MEASURED FORCE-DISPLACEMENT

Figure 3 shows typical records for the strain gage history taken from the incident and transmitter bars. As can be seen from the figure there are a sufficient number of data points collected, even in the rise of the pulse. These histories are then used to produce force and displacement histories and then force vs. displacement results. Hopkinson bar experiments were conducted at two impact velocities. A striker velocity of approximately 13 m/s was the minimum velocity resulting in complete penetration with the longer pulse produced by the long striker and 18 m/s was the maximum velocity that could be used based on the limitations imposed by keeping the bars in the elastic range. Each experiment was repeated and fairly good repeatability obtained, at least up to the point of the peak load.

Figure 3. Typical strain gage readings on incident and transmitter bars

The results from three of the deformation rates are superimposed in Fig. 4. Results are presented comparing average punch speed, which is the displacement at the peak load divided by the time. Note that for clarity of presentation some smoothing of the data was performed. At the two slower rates in the figure little difference is seen, although the slope is somewhat greater at the higher rate. At the highest rate, though, considerable difference is noted in the slope with an increase of approximately one-third. There also is a well-defined plateau that occurs at approximately 22 kN, which is not apparent in the slower rate experiments. At that point the load increases sharply to the peak load. As seen in the figure there is little variation in the peak load over the range of rates. Possible reasons for this will be discussed subsequently. Beyond the peak the data taken at lower rates is insufficient for any conclusions as described above, but at the higher rate it can be seen that failure is not instantaneous, but rather continues progressively with numerous subsequent peaks.

Figure 4. Load displacement results for different average punching velocities

Figure 5. Results for partial penetration at 8 m/s and 10 m/s compared to complete penetration

Several experiments were conducted using the Hopkinson bar apparatus with the long striker at slower velocities. These velocities are insufficient to cause complete penetration of the specimen, but do provide load-displacement results at the lower rates to some load below the peak. Fig. 5 shows the smoothed load-displacement results for striker velocities of 8 m/s and 10 m/s as well as results for complete penetration at 18 m/s. Here it can be seen that the plateau described above at 21 kN is still present, but occurs at a lower load for the experiments conducted at lower striker velocities.

POST-TEST OBSERVATIONS

X-ray inspection of specimens was utilized to investigate the extent of damage. The dye utilized was 1,4-Diiodobutane manufactured by the Aldrich Chemical Co. Die was applied to the edges of the specimen at one hour intervals for four applications. In this way die will accumulate in regions of cracking, thus showing damage on the outside of the plug region. X-rays were then taken in a Hewlett-Packard Faxitron series X-ray system, using a 10 sec exposure at a tube voltage of 20 V. X-rays of specimens loaded to 15 kN show no damage whereas a specimen loaded to 25 kN shows the beginning of a ring at the center of the specimen. The cracking is limited to the punched region. Figure 6a is of a completely punched specimen still showing damage only at the edge of the punched hole. The damage zone surrounding the punch is estimated from the figure to be approximately 0.5 to 1.0 mm wide. Figure 6b shows a specimen loaded to 31kN. In this case dye is applied to the plug, thus showing the extent of delamination. Comparison of X-rays of specimens tested at the various rates showed no observable difference in the damaged region. In addition to the X-ray investigation, visual inspection of sectioned specimens was made using an optical microscope, which was linked to a digital camera. Results were enhanced on a Macintosh personal computer. Visual inspection is made easier by the presence of white lines, which are the plies in which the fibers are parallel to the cutting plane. The results have been used to study the evolution of damage and failure. Figure 7 shows a cut specimen which had been loaded from the lower side of the photograph to 31 kN, which is just below peak load. Damage in the form of delamination is clearly apparent in the specimen. Figure 8 shows a specimen loaded beyond the peak load and here it is seen that all of the layers have been fractured and are beginning to be pushed out. As indicated by the 0 degree layers closest to the punch side, considerable rotation of the fibers has taken place.

Figure 6. X-rays of post test specimens a) completely punched b) damage within the plug

Figure 7. Sectioned specimen loaded to 31kN

Figure 8. Sectioned specimen loaded beyond peak load

DISCUSSION

From the load-displacement results presented, it is clear that there is a rate-effect present during the loading portion of the material response, but the effect of rate is small for maximum load achieved during punching. By using the post-test observation, a plausible explanation for this is developed. During the early stages of loading the dominant stress field in the specimen is transverse shear, which in large part is determined by the response of the matrix. However, after delamination cracking has developed significant material rotation takes place as can be seen in Fig. 8. With the material rotation, the fibers become loaded in tension, and it is then the tensile strength of the fibers that determines the peak punch load. As has been shown by Harding and Welsh [5], the tensile strength of graphite/epoxy composites shows little rate effect, which would be consistent with little rate effect in maximum punch load.

The effect of rate in the transverse shear response is most apparent from the presence of a plateau in the load-displacement curves for the high rate experiments, which does not occur in the slower ones. After the plateau the specimens are loaded again, along a path which is quite similar to the load path at the lower rates. This can be seen clearly in Fig. 4. With these results the load-displacement response at the low rate can be considered to be some type of equilibrium response. At higher rates the material is stiffer as demonstrated by the higher initial slope, but after some critical amount of damage occurs in the material, the response relaxes back to the equilibrium response.

CONCLUSIONS

We have presented here only force vs. displacement results from the experiments since they can be obtained directly from the strain gage readings on the Hopkinson bar, assuming only that one-dimensional elastic wave propagation theory holds for the bars. Conversion of these results to stress vs. strain requires an assumption to be made on the gage length which is particularly difficult for determining nominal strain. Nominal stress results can be obtained by taking the load divided by the circumferential area. This would result in a peak stress of approximately 325 MPa. The plateau found during the high rate tests, which could be representative of significant damage accumulation occurs at nominal stresses of 175 MPa to 215 MPa. Estimates of strain and strain rate that occur vary significantly depending on the gage length assumed. A lower bound on the gage length would be the radial clearance between the punch and the die (0.03 mm) and an upper bound might be the damage region seen in the post test observations (1.0 mm), which is probably more realistic. Using this estimate the engineering strain at which delamination damage is detected is approximately .20 and the maximum nominal rates obtained during the experiments is 4000 s^{-1} .

It is expected that a better description of the distribution of stress, strain, and strain rate will be obtained by utilizing finite element analysis of the experimental configuration and that the combination of the analysis and experimental results can be used to help determine appropriate constitutive models for laminated composite materials undergoing damage during high rate loading. These studies are ongoing and will be reported subsequently.

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MECHANICAL PROPERTIES: TEXTILE
